

Data summary

Figure S1: Number of datapoints used per species and per dataset from each year. MAS: Meetnet Agrarische Soorten; MUS: Meetnet Urbane Soorten; CBC: Common Bird Census. French data comes from Suivi Temporel des Oiseaux Communs. Data from recent years was excluded for blackbirds due to the effect of recent Usutu virus outbreaks.

Figure S2: Number of datapoints used per species and per dataset from each Dutch province. MAS: Meetnet Agrarische Soorten; MUS: Meetnet Urbane Soorten; CBC: Common Bird Census.

Figure S3: Number of datapoints used per species from each French region. French data comes from Suivi Temporel des Oiseaux Communs.

Figure S4: Number of datapoints used per species and per dataset for different numbers of birds observed. MAS: Meetnet Agrarische Soorten; MUS: Meetnet Urbane Soorten; CBC: Common Bird Census. French data comes from Suivi Temporel des Oiseaux Communs.